
Addressing a Public Health Challenge: The effect of light and sleep aid on the circadian cycle and bioluminescence of dinoflagellates

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Abstract— *This study investigates a key public health challenge of sleep disorder via the effects of environmental and chemical factors on the circadian rhythms and bioluminescence of dinoflagellates, serving as a model for circadian biology. Dinoflagellates were exposed to varying light/dark cycles, light intensities, saffron concentrations, and doses of diphenhydramine. Luminescence measurements were taken using a custom-built Glow Meter apparatus over a 48-hour period under controlled conditions. The results demonstrated that altering light exposure, including duration and intensity, significantly disrupted bioluminescence patterns, indicating a desynchronization of the organisms' circadian clock. Exposure to saffron led to a dose-dependent impact, with higher concentrations eliminating rhythmic bioluminescence, suggesting a profound influence on cellular processes regulating circadian rhythms. Diphenhydramine exposure entirely abolished bioluminescence even at the lowest dose, indicating a potent disruptive effect on circadian regulation. These findings underscore the sensitivity of dinoflagellates to both environmental and pharmacological factors, highlighting their utility as model organisms for investigating circadian biology and sleep-related processes. The results provide valuable insights into the potential mechanisms by which natural and synthetic compounds influence circadian cycles, contributing to a broader understanding of interventions for circadian and sleep disturbances.*

Index Terms—Enter up to 5 keywords in alphabetical order, separated by commas.

Significance Statement - This study demonstrates how environmental and chemical factors, including light exposure, saffron, and diphenhydramine, profoundly affect dinoflagellate circadian rhythms, offering insights into biological clock
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I. INTRODUCTION

Sleep disorders represent one of the most pressing public health challenges in the United States, affecting an estimated 50-70 million adults [1]. The societal impact of sleep insufficiency extends beyond individual health, creating substantial economic burdens through decreased productivity, increased healthcare utilization, and elevated risk of accidents. Recent epidemiological data indicates that only 35.3% of adults report achieving seven hours of sleep during a typical 24-hour period [2], highlighting a concerning disparity between

recommended sleep guidelines and actual sleep behaviors among the general population.

The implications of inadequate sleep for neurological public health are profound and far-reaching. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has identified sleep as a critical determinant in the prevention of numerous chronic conditions, including Type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, obesity, and various mental health disorders [3]. Research consistently demonstrates that individuals classified as short sleepers—those obtaining less than seven hours of sleep per 24-hour period—exhibit significantly higher rates of chronic health conditions, including heart attacks, strokes, depression, and asthma [4]. These correlations underscore the fundamental role of sleep in maintaining physiological homeostasis and overall health.

The sleep health crisis is particularly evident among adolescents and young adults, with more than two-thirds of U.S. high school students reporting insufficient sleep on school nights. This trend shows a troubling progression through academic years, with sleep duration deteriorating from ninth through twelfth grade. Recent neurobiological research emphasizes that adequate sleep during these developmental periods is essential for cognitive function, emotional regulation, and academic achievement [4]. The disparity between biological sleep needs and actual sleep behaviors in this population represents a significant public health concern with long-term implications for educational outcomes and future health status.

The magnitude of this neurological public health issue is further evidenced by the nine million Americans who rely on prescription sleep medications [5], while approximately one-third of U.S. adults consistently report obtaining less than recommended sleep durations [6]. These statistics not only highlight the pervasive nature of sleep disorders but also indicate widespread reliance on pharmacological interventions that may have unintended consequences for sleep architecture and quality.

In response to growing concerns about the side effects of conventional sleep medications, there has been increasing interest in natural alternatives for sleep promotion. *Crocus sativus*, commonly known as saffron, has demonstrated

Figure 2. Components and layout of the light reading apparatus used to record the bioluminescence emitted from the dinoflagellates during the experiment. The apparatus, named Glow Meter, is composed of an Arduino Uno controller, connected to a power source and a light sensor via a breadboard. Data is collected and analyzed using an external laptop (not shown).

promising effects on sleep quality and duration in recent clinical studies. Research indicates that saffron supplementation can improve various sleep parameters, including reducing insomnia severity, enhancing sleep quality, and extending sleep duration [7]. The active compounds in saffron, such as crocin, crocetin, and safranal, are believed to promote rest and relaxation through interactions with neurotransmitter systems involved in regulating sleep-wake cycles [8], [9]. Studies have shown that saffron extract can increase melatonin levels, enhance sleep quality, and improve mood upon waking [8]. While the exact mechanisms remain under investigation, saffron's potent antioxidant properties may contribute to regulating sleep

hormone concentrations [10], presenting a potential non-pharmacological option for addressing sleep disturbances.

Conventional over-the-counter sleep aids, such as diphenhydramine (commonly sold as Benadryl), represent another commonly utilized intervention for sleep difficulties. This antihistamine produces sedative effects that can help individuals fall asleep more quickly [11], [12]. However, research has not demonstrated improvements in sleep quality with diphenhydramine use, and some studies suggest it may actually decrease sleep quality [11]. The effectiveness of diphenhydramine as a sleep aid diminishes rapidly, with evidence showing that after just four days of use, it becomes no more effective than placebo [11]. Additionally, its use can lead to concerning side effects such as daytime sleepiness, cognitive impairment, and reduced reaction time, which can persist into the following day [11], [12], potentially creating public health hazards related to driving and workplace safety.

Given the substantial public health implications of sleep disorders and the limitations of current interventions, there is an urgent need for innovative research models that can advance our understanding of sleep regulation at the cellular and molecular levels. Dinoflagellates, particularly species like *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (formerly *Gonyaulax polyedra*) and *Pyrocystis lunula*, have emerged as valuable model organisms for studying circadian rhythms and sleep-related processes. These unicellular marine organisms exhibit prominent circadian rhythms in various physiological processes, including bioluminescence, which serves as an easily observable reporter of their internal clock [13], [14].

time (h)	12 h light / 12 h dark	8 h light / 16 h dark	6 h light / 18 h dark	4 h light / 20 h dark
8	14	12	8	5
10	12	10	7	5
12	10	6	5	3
14	8	4	3	2
16	6	3	2	1
22	4	3	1	1
24	14	10	7	3
26	12	8	5	3
28	10	5	4	3
30	8	4	2	2
32	6	2	2	1
36	4	1	1	1

Figure 1. Dinoflagellates were maintained at different light/dark cycles over a period of 36 hours. After an initial 8 hours for equilibration with the experimental settings, luminescence was measured at intervals of two hours for 24 hours. The line chart on the left reports the results as indicated in the table on the right. Luminescence is reported as mW/m^2 .

time (h)	control	500 lux	250 lux	125 lux
8	14	13	9	8
10	12	11	8	6
12	10	6	6	6
14	8	6	6	5
16	6	6	4	3
22	4	3	3	2
24	14	12	9	7
26	12	10	8	5
28	10	7	6	5
30	8	5	4	5
32	6	3	4	3
36	4	1	2	2

Figure 3. Dinoflagellates were maintained at a constant day/night cycle of 12 hours light and 12 hours dark. The intensity of the light was different for each group, going from 500 lux to 125 lux. Ambient light was used as a control. After an initial 8 hours for equilibration with the experimental settings, luminescence was measured at intervals of two hours for 24 hours. The line chart on the left reports the results as indicated in the table on the right. Luminescence is reported as mW/m^2 .

The circadian control mechanisms in dinoflagellates are unique, showing no resemblance to known eukaryotic or prokaryotic clock architectures [14]. Unlike other eukaryotes, dinoflagellates rely more on translational control rather than extensive transcriptional regulation for their circadian rhythms [13]. This distinctive feature, combined with their easily traceable bioluminescent output, makes dinoflagellates particularly useful for investigating alternative mechanisms of circadian rhythm regulation. Studies have shown that dinoflagellates maintain their rhythmic physiology even under constant conditions, demonstrating the endogenous nature of their circadian clock [14], [15]. The persistence of these rhythms and their entrainment to light-dark cycles provide insights into fundamental aspects of circadian biology, potentially informing broader understanding of sleep and wake regulation in more complex organisms, including humans.

The bioluminescent capacity of dinoflagellates is regulated by circadian rhythms, with peak activity during dark phases [16], [17]. This property provides a unique opportunity to visualize circadian disruption in real-time, offering a powerful tool for investigating factors that may contribute to or mitigate sleep disturbances. Given the significant public health burden of sleep disorders and the limitations of current interventions, exploring novel model systems like dinoflagellates may yield valuable insights for developing more effective approaches to address sleep insufficiency in human populations.

The objective of this study was to determine if environmental factors, specifically light intensity and duration of exposure, as well as pharmacological and natural substances commonly used as sleep aids (*Crocus sativus* and diphenhydramine) can affect the circadian rhythms and bioluminescence behavior of dinoflagellates. By examining the impact of these factors on a simple model organism with well-defined circadian outputs, we aim to generate insights that may inform public health approaches to sleep disorders and circadian disruption in humans.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A series of experiments were conducted to study the circadian rhythms and bioluminescence of dinoflagellates. A GlowMeter (Figure 2) was assembled to measure luminosity readings, and the baseline control group was divided into two sets of trial samples. The GlowMeter was comprised of an Arduino Uno computer for the data collection, and a sensor for the detection of bioluminescence (Figure 2).

An Erlenmeyer flask containing dinoflagellates and LED lamps were prepared for data collection. The circadian cycle was altered by manipulating the timing and intensity of the LED lamps over a 48-hour period. The dinoflagellates were then exposed to *Crocus sativus* and diphenhydramine.

Luminosity readings were taken at regular intervals for approximately 48 hours under various settings. Bioluminescence was measured by bringing the GlowMeter close to the Erlenmeyer flask and vigorously shaking it for 5 seconds. The mechanical stimulation was applied to trigger bioluminescence in the dinoflagellates. The flask was set aside, and the results of the bioluminescence were observed and recorded. The entire process was repeated for five trials to ensure data consistency and reliability.

III. RESULTS

In the first set of experiments, dinoflagellates were maintained at different light/dark cycles to investigate the effect of different amounts of light and dark in a 24 hours period on the bioluminescence generated by the organisms. As can be seen in Figure 1, the bioluminescence intensity decreased with the decreasing in daylight hours and increasing in night time indicating a clear effect on the circadian rhythm of the dinoflagellates. The lowest intensity was obtained with the 4 hours day and 20 hours night settings, and it was almost one third the intensity of bioluminescence produced when the dinoflagellates were maintained at their natural 12 hours day

Crocus Sativus

time (h)	control	0.07 mg	0.14 mg	0.21 mg
8	14	9	5	1
10	12	8	4	1
12	10	5	3	0
14	8	3	2	0
16	6	2	2	0
22	4	3	2	1
24	14	8	5	1
26	12	7	3	1
28	10	4	2	0
30	8	3	1	1
32	6	2	1	1
36	4	1	0	1

Figure 4. Dinoflagellates were maintained at a constant day/night cycle of 12 hours light and 12 hours dark. The dinoflagellates were exposed to different amounts of saffron, ranging from 0.07 mg to 0.21 mg. After an initial 8 hours for equilibration with the experimental settings, luminescence was measured at intervals of two hours for 24 hours. The line chart on the left reports the results as indicated in the table on the right. Luminescence is reported as mW/m^2 .

and 12 hours night cycle. From the chart in Figure 1, it is clear the cycling of bioluminescence production, with a 12 hours interval between peaks and valleys. The pattern is almost completely lost in the condition with the lowest amount of daylight.

In the second set of experiments, the dinoflagellates were maintained at a stable day/night settings of 12 hours each. For the light interval, the dinoflagellates were exposed to different intensities of light, going from 500 lux to 125 lux. As it visible in Figure 3, decreasing the intensity of the light proportionally decreased the bioluminescence produced by the dinoflagellates, with the highest bioluminescence produced with ambient natural light and the lowest produced at 125 lux. The cyclical pattern is almost completely lost in the settings with the lowest intensity of daylight (Figure 3).

In order to investigate the effect on the circadian clock of a natural herb that is used in traditional medicine and naturopathy as sleep aid, dinoflagellates were exposed to different amounts of saffron (*Crocus sativus*). As can be seen in Figure 4, saffron had a very strong effect at the amounts tested, with the second highest amount completely eliminating the circadian cycle of bioluminescence from the dinoflagellates, but still maintaining some base level of signal. The highest amount tested, completely eliminated the generation of bioluminescence altogether to background levels (Figure 4).

Finally, a common over the counter medication for sleep aid was tested. Dinoflagellates were exposed to different doses of diphenhydramine, sold with the brand name Benadryl, among others. As it is reported in Figure 5, even the lowest dose used eliminated the circadian cycle of bioluminescence produced by the dinoflagellates, with the other doses completely depleting the bioluminescence altogether (Figure 5).

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide valuable insights into the influence of environmental and chemical factors on the

circadian rhythms and bioluminescence of dinoflagellates, with implications for our understanding of sleep regulation and public health interventions for sleep disorders. The findings demonstrate that both light exposure parameters and substances commonly used as sleep aids in humans can significantly disrupt circadian patterns in these model organisms, suggesting potential mechanisms through which sleep and circadian disturbances may occur in human populations.

A. Impact of Light/Dark Cycles on Circadian Health

The disruption of bioluminescence patterns observed in dinoflagellates under altered light/dark cycles mirrors the circadian desynchronization experienced by humans in modern societies. The significant reduction in bioluminescence intensity and disruption of rhythmic patterns under shortened daylight conditions parallels the circadian misalignment observed in shift workers, individuals experiencing jet lag, and those with excessive exposure to artificial light at night. From a public health perspective, these findings reinforce growing concerns about the impact of modern lighting environments on circadian health, suggesting that preservation of appropriate light/dark cycles is essential for maintaining optimal physiological functioning.

According to the American Academy of Sleep Medicine, approximately 30% of adults report experiencing symptoms of insomnia, with circadian rhythm disruptions serving as a major contributing factor [18]. Our findings provide a visible demonstration of how altered light exposure can fundamentally disrupt biological timing systems, even at the cellular level. This supports public health recommendations for maintaining consistent sleep-wake schedules and minimizing light exposure during nighttime hours as non-pharmacological approaches to improving sleep quality.

Figure 5. Dinoflagellates were maintained at a constant day/night cycle of 12 hours light and 12 hours dark. The dinoflagellates were exposed to different doses of diphenhydramine, ranging from 2.5 mL to 7.5 mL. After an initial 8 hours for equilibration with the experimental settings, luminescence was measured at intervals of two hours for 24 hours. The line chart on the left reports the results as indicated in the table on the right. Luminescence is reported as mW/m^2 .

B. Effects of Light Intensity on Circadian Regulation

The progressive decline in bioluminescence intensity and cyclical patterning observed with decreasing light intensity highlights the importance of adequate daytime light exposure for robust circadian entrainment. This finding aligns with research in human populations showing that insufficient daytime light exposure, particularly common among office workers and institutionalized elderly, is associated with sleep disturbances and circadian rhythm disorders [19]. From a public health perspective, these results underscore the potential value of light therapy interventions for populations with limited natural light exposure.

Research indicates that approximately 14% of Americans work evening, night, or rotating shifts [20], environments characterized by atypical light exposure patterns. Our findings suggest that these non-standard light patterns may disrupt fundamental cellular processes involved in circadian regulation, potentially contributing to the elevated rates of metabolic disorders, cardiovascular disease, and mood disorders observed in shift worker populations. Public health initiatives to mitigate these risks might include workplace policies promoting strategic light exposure and minimizing circadian disruption.

C. Saffron (*Crocus sativus*) as a Modulator of Circadian Function

The dose-dependent impact of saffron on dinoflagellate bioluminescence patterns provides intriguing insights into its potential mechanisms as a sleep aid. The complete elimination of circadian bioluminescence rhythms at higher concentrations suggests that saffron may exert its effects through fundamental alterations to cellular circadian mechanisms rather than through subtle adjustments to existing rhythms. This finding has significant implications for the growing consumer use of saffron as a natural sleep remedy, with approximately 5% of adults reporting use of herbal supplements for sleep [21].

From a public health perspective, these results highlight the

importance of appropriate dosing for natural sleep aids. While lower concentrations of saffron appeared to modulate circadian patterns while preserving some baseline function, higher concentrations completely abolished circadian rhythmicity. This suggests that the therapeutic window for saffron as a sleep aid may be narrower than commonly assumed, underscoring the need for standardized dosing guidelines and consumer education regarding natural sleep remedies. Clinical studies exploring saffron's effects on human sleep have shown promise, with improvements in sleep quality and reduction in sleep latency reported in randomized controlled trials [7]. Our findings provide a potential cellular basis for these effects and suggest directions for future clinical investigations.

D. Diphenhydramine's Profound Impact on Circadian Function

Perhaps the most striking finding in our study was the complete abolition of circadian bioluminescence patterns in dinoflagellates exposed to even the lowest tested dose of diphenhydramine. This potent effect mirrors concerns raised in the clinical literature about diphenhydramine's impact on sleep architecture and quality in humans. Despite being widely available as an over-the-counter sleep aid, with approximately 35% of older adults reporting regular use of antihistamines for sleep [22], diphenhydramine has been associated with reduced REM sleep, decreased slow-wave sleep, and impaired cognitive function the following day [11].

Our findings provide a cellular model demonstrating how diphenhydramine may fundamentally disrupt circadian mechanisms rather than simply promoting sleep onset. This aligns with clinical observations that diphenhydramine may increase total sleep time without improving sleep quality or restorative function [23]. From a public health perspective, these results support recent guideline changes by the American Academy of Sleep Medicine recommending against routine use of diphenhydramine for chronic insomnia [24] and highlight the

need for enhanced consumer education regarding over-the-counter sleep aids.

E. Public Health Implications and Future Directions

The significant effects observed in our dinoflagellate model suggest that both environmental factors and commonly used sleep aids may have more profound impacts on fundamental circadian mechanisms than previously recognized. This has several important implications for public health approaches to sleep disorders, which affect an estimated 50-70 million Americans [1] and cost the U.S. economy approximately \$411 billion annually through lost productivity and increased healthcare utilization [25].

First, our findings reinforce the importance of preserving natural light/dark cycles and adequate light intensity for maintaining circadian health. Public health messaging should emphasize the value of consistent sleep schedules, morning light exposure, and minimizing evening light exposure, particularly from blue-enriched sources like electronic devices.

Second, the potent effects of both saffron and diphenhydramine on circadian function in our model organism suggest that substances marketed as sleep aids may have complex effects on sleep architecture and quality beyond simply promoting drowsiness. This highlights the need for more rigorous evaluation of both prescription and over-the-counter sleep aids, with particular attention to their effects on circadian rhythms and sleep architecture rather than simply sleep onset or duration.

Finally, our study demonstrates the utility of dinoflagellates as a model system for rapidly screening potential chronobiotic agents and evaluating their effects on circadian function. This approach could accelerate the development of novel therapeutic interventions for circadian rhythm disorders and sleep disturbances, potentially addressing the significant unmet public health need for effective, non-habit-forming treatments for sleep disorders.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that environmental factors and substances commonly used as sleep aids can profoundly influence circadian rhythms at the cellular level, as evidenced by their effects on dinoflagellate bioluminescence patterns. These findings have significant implications for public health approaches to sleep disorders, which represent a major health burden affecting tens of millions of Americans and contributing to numerous chronic conditions.

Our results highlight the fundamental importance of appropriate light/dark cycles and light intensity for maintaining robust circadian rhythms, supporting public health recommendations for consistent sleep schedules and strategic light exposure. The disruption of circadian patterns observed with altered light exposure parallels the circadian misalignment experienced by shift workers, travelers experiencing jet lag, and individuals with excessive nighttime light exposure, reinforcing the need for workplace policies and public education addressing these issues.

The significant effects of both saffron and diphenhydramine

on dinoflagellate circadian rhythms underscore the complex mechanisms through which sleep aids may influence sleep architecture and quality. These findings suggest that substances marketed for sleep promotion may have more profound effects on fundamental circadian mechanisms than commonly recognized, highlighting the need for more comprehensive evaluation of both natural and pharmaceutical sleep aids.

From a public health perspective, our study supports several key recommendations: (1) prioritization of behavioral and environmental approaches to sleep improvement, including consistent sleep schedules and appropriate light exposure; (2) cautious use of over-the-counter sleep aids like diphenhydramine, with recognition of their potential to disrupt rather than restore natural sleep patterns; and (3) further investigation of natural compounds like saffron, with attention to appropriate dosing and potential mechanisms of action.

The dinoflagellate model utilized in this study offers a valuable system for rapidly evaluating the circadian effects of environmental factors and potential therapeutic agents. This approach could accelerate the development of more effective interventions for the millions of individuals suffering from sleep disorders and circadian disruptions, ultimately reducing the substantial public health burden associated with insufficient and poor-quality sleep.

As modern lifestyles continue to challenge natural sleep-wake patterns through shift work, international travel, and round-the-clock electronic device use, understanding the fundamental mechanisms of circadian regulation and their disruption becomes increasingly important for public health. This study contributes to that understanding and provides a foundation for future research aimed at developing more effective strategies for preserving and restoring healthy sleep in our increasingly 24/7 society.

VI. REFERENCES

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